

WP5 - Getting actors to act: dissemination, exploitation and communication

<p>Beneficiaries of AF products and services</p>		
<p>“I need to find solutions to meet SDGs and European Green Deal targets, and I want to know the impact the CAP”</p>	<p>“I believe we have to move to sustainable agriculture so I want to try something new and see a growing potential</p>	<p>“I am looking for new options to create carbon credits and I am preparing our story on biodiversity credits.” “</p>

Practice abstracts (batch1)

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1 Context

The DigitAF research project (July 2022 - June 2026), funded by the European Commission, aims at a high quality implementation of agroforestry to foster climate change mitigation and adaptation in agriculture and to ensure sustainable management of natural resources. Our goal is to provide the main actor groups with tools answering their needs, in particular digital tools. The three actors' groups that are target by DigitAF are:

- Policy actors: policymakers and administrations concerned with applying agroforestry -related regulations, at regional, national and European levels, who set the scene for the adoption (or not) of agroforestry.
- Practitioners: farmers, landowners and by extension, farm advisers playing an active role in designing and managing AFS and whose choices determine the agronomic, economic, environmental, and social performance at farm-level and beyond.
- Beneficiaries of AF products and services: stakeholders in the value chain, including wholesalers, retailers, organisations trading the carbon sequestration and biodiversity benefits of AFS, and final consumers seeking verification of the benefits of AF in clear and accessible terms.

This report is relevant for the communication about the project and dissemination to all three stakeholders' groups. It contains the information asked for in the EIP agri common format template (the same information in excel format is available upon request).

2 Project information

DIGital Tools to help AgroForestry meet climate, biodiversity and farming sustainability goals: linking field and cloud.

Table 1 - Information required by the European Practice Abstract template

Project identifier	2022HORIZON_101059794_DigitAF
Title of the project in English	DigitAF: DIGital Tools to help AgroForestry meet climate, biodiversity and farming sustainability goals: linking field and cloud
Country (of the coordinator)	FR
Main geographical location (NUTS3)	FR813 - Hérault
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Project period:	2022 - 2026
Project status:	ongoing
Main funding source	Horizon Europe
Total budget	3 667 138.00 €

Objective of the project in English:	<p>Agroforestry (AF) has already proven its potential for farm sustainability, climate change mitigation and adaptation, biodiversity preservation, and soil conservation. However, AF performances are context-dependent, and many barriers hinder its adoption, such as lack of tools for decision-making, assessing economic, environmental, social benefits, and monitoring of policies and their impact on AF. DigitAF will boost AF implementation in the EU and beyond thanks to the co-development of digital tools tailored to the needs and concerns of DigitAF target groups (policy-actors, practitioners value chains).</p>
Objective of the project in native language	<p>L'agroforesterie (AF) est prometteuse pour répondre aux enjeux de durabilité des exploitations agricoles mais ses performances dépendent du contexte et de nombreux obstacles entravent son adoption, tels que le manque d'outils d'aide à la décision, d'évaluation des avantages de l'AF et de suivi des politiques publiques et de leur impact. DigitAF stimulera la mise en œuvre de l'AF dans l'UE et au-delà grâce au co-développement d'outils numériques adaptés aux besoins et aux préoccupations des groupes cibles de DigitAF (acteurs politiques, praticiens, chaînes de valeur).</p>
Description of project activities in English:	<p>The project will provide open-source digital tools to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support policymakers and administrations in devising and implementing efficient AF- and carbon farming related policies, and monitor their results • support practitioners of AF to optimise the design and management of AFS to increase the technical feasibility, productivity, economic performance, and sustainability • Allow AF products and services beneficiaries to quantify and verify AF benefits in value chains • facilitate interactions between actors through 6 living labs and offer open-source data and AF tools catalogue and development space • communicate, disseminate, and exploit DigitAF's results and AF in general
Description of project activities in native language:	<p>Nous synthétiserons les politiques relatives à l'AF en Europe et adapterons les outils de reporting et de calcul utilisé pour mesurer l'impact des politiques incitatives sur le nombre d'arbres hors forêt et la fourniture de services environnementaux. Nous rendrons opérationnelles les connaissances scientifiques en fournissant des outils d'aide à la décision et/ou des indicateurs faciles à mesurer pour la conception, l'évaluation et la gestion des systèmes agroforestiers. Enfin, nous améliorerons la valorisation des produits et services agroforestiers grâce à des outils pour vérifier les bénéfices de l'agroforesterie sur la biodiversité, la séquestration du C et la santé des sols.</p>
Description of the context of the project in English	<p>Up to now, policy efforts to support AF adoption have failed. Although AF is recognised as one of the most effective climate change mitigation measures, few MS had successfully supported it in their recent funding programmes: AF was included in only 35 of the 118 2014-2020 Development Programmes, and by the end of 2019, only six countries and 30 regions had implemented AF support, spending only 3.3 M€ out of the 130 M€ initially planned. Farmers' concerns include the technical feasibility of AF, difficulty to predict the impact of their choices made and lack of recognition of AF benefits. AF is complex and need to be tailored to each farm's local context and each farmer's objectives. Recent scientific</p>

	<p>results have improved the understanding of the functioning of AF and the impact of AF on farm profitability, but this knowledge is often context-specific, with insufficient options for extrapolation to other conditions, and not accessible in a user-friendly way. Furthermore, we still miss critical insights into using AF as a tool to address major challenges that farmers face, such as soil and water conservation, pesticide and other inputs reduction, climate change adaptation and farm viability. Some of the other barriers to the expansion of AF are caused by constraints in the value chains: problems in ensuring robust contracts and coordination between actors. Many of the benefits of AF beyond the farm-gate are inadequately quantified. Therefore, actors in the value chain need tools to verify and account for AF benefits (e.g. biodiversity, carbon, soil health, and animal welfare), so that they can recognize and valorize AF products and services.</p>
<p>Additional information on the project in English</p>	<p>The wider agricultural sector is rapidly being digitised. It creates new opportunities for farmers and advisers to leverage this technology to improve their financial and ecological performances, and many European farmers are already using DSS to support them in their daily work at the field and management level. These tools collect, combine, and analyse a range of data, including field data from sensors and satellite images and meteorological data, and provide data-driven support and information on optimizing production and/or quality. However, the development of such tools for AF is still in its infancy. DigitAF partners believe that by combining simulation models and data, it is possible to create digital tools supporting decision-makers to better (i) understand the complex functioning of AFS, (ii) consider local specificities and (iii) make better decisions. Existing tools were developed somewhat independently, without much thought on web 2.0/3.0 concepts. Therefore, there are limited data sharing standards to describe AF and allow interoperability between the different models and tools. This results in duplicate data entries, difficulties for using outputs of one model as inputs for another one, and the impossibility to reuse modules of one model in new models. DigitAF will set up the necessary standards, IT architecture and code sharing opportunities so that tools will overcome these problems. Tools adapted/developed during the project will serve as demonstration vectors for engagement towards the FAIR principles to boost their usage and applicability between peers (other researchers, students, etc.) and downstream marketable applied tools.</p>

3 What is the CAP doing (or not) for agroforestry? Support offered in 14 Member States and the need to do more if we are to meet GHG targets

A step forward for agroforestry in the current CAP is that all Member States (MS) now have a national definition of what the term means for them - on arable land, permanent crops and permanent grassland (EURAF [Policy Briefing #22](#)), and have rules for “landscape features”, including lines of trees, hedges, groups of trees, and isolated trees, including permitted group sizes and spacings ([Policy Briefing #21](#)). For most MS, woody-landscape-features are a form of agroforestry, and MS are required to report annually (as part of Result Indicator 17) on the areas of agroforestry and new woody-landscape-features. But not all MS will do this, since in six countries forestry and agroforestry are financed from outside the CAP and no statistics are available ([Policy Briefing #19](#)). Explicit support for agroforestry is disappointingly low in the 14 MS analysed: ecoschemes in 2MS, Pillar II - AECM schemes in 4MS, Pillar II Investment schemes in 7MS (see figure below). Even in these cases, some schemes

have been adopted by only a few regions or are very poorly funded - e.g. the agroforestry eco-scheme in Germany paid only 60 €/ha and attracted a total of 55 farmers in its first year! MS are required to review their CAP plans by the end of 2023 to ensure that they generate the national share of the -310 MtCO₂e EU sequestration for 2030 stipulated in the revised LULUCF Regulation (May 2023). Collectively, the CAP plans fall far short of this - especially in the area of afforestation and agroforestation ([Policy Briefing #26](#)). Hopefully, Member States will take the opportunity to correct this before the end of 2023. Stay tuned on DigitAF (<https://digitaf.eu>) and EURAF (<https://euraf.net/category/policy-briefings>) websites to get updates.

Country	Ecoschemes	Pillar-II AECMs	Pillar II - INVEST
BE-FL	n	y	y
CZ	n	y	y
DK	n	n	n
FI	n	n	n
FR	(y)	y	y
FI	n	n	n
DE	y	n	(y)
GR	y	n	n
HU	x	x	y
IT	x	x	y
LV	x	x	x
NL	(y)	n	(y)
PT	(y)	y	y
SL	n	n	n
ES	(y)	(y)	y
TOTAL	2	4	7

4 Which tree(s) for my agroforestry plot? We help you find the best DSS for tree selection.

The selection of species to be combined in agroforestry is a thorny issue: trees not only need to be adapted to local conditions (soil, climate...), but also to meet the farmer's objectives, both in terms of production (wood, fruit or nuts, biomass) and services (protection against extreme events, maintenance of biodiversity...). Several research teams, as well as technical institutes and even private companies, have addressed this question and proposed decision support systems to facilitate this choice. However, it can be difficult for a farmer to find the right tool for his or her situation (type of system, pedo-climatic or socio-economic context...). In the DigitAF project, we are listing these tools and we are currently testing and evaluating them for you. What's more, we are building a single tool that will soon enable access to all these tools through a single interface. Now that's going to make your life a whole lot easier! For now, we have worked on:

- DENTRO (a tool developed in Belgium to choose among 80 species of trees for silvoarable and silvopastoral systems)
- DECIDUOUS (a tool developed in France to select among 33 rootstocks for fruit trees in agroforestry systems)
- SCSM (a tool to select trees among 441 species, both tropical and temperate)
- ShadeTreeAdvice (a tool specifically designed to select shade trees in coffee and cocoa agroforestry systems, with 215 possible species).

To see the progress of this work, stay tuned on our website (<https://digitaf.eu>) or, if you like coding, contribute directly on <https://github.com/euraf/agroforestreeadvice>

5 Digital support tools for agroforestry design and management: how can we increase their user-friendliness and make them communicate with each other?

Though agroforestry is still considered a niche compared to traditional agriculture, dedicated models and tools for agroforestry have been around for decades. However, it's only recently, with the advancement of the web, that the possibility to leverage open datasets and integrate with other tools and models, have really become feasible. Models that were previously only available to expert researchers can now become available for farmers and other practitioners with the click of a button, thanks to standardized formats and protocols, which makes it possible for different tools and models to communicate with each other. This ultimately creates more value for the people that use the tools and models since they can have access to a whole new range of functions, that were previously not available. In the DigitAF project, work has been done to assess (and establish definitions) how tools and models can communicate with each other through shared language and protocols, to further improve the integration of tools and models and make it even easier for researchers and developers to combine different tools and models. At early stages of this assessment, we need to know which tools are available, how they are made available, and whether it is possible to integrate them and work in collaborations to develop them. Amongst these initial steps we are wrapping up an online agroforestry tool database (<https://digitaf.eu/tools-database>) that will enable not only access to the tools, but also understanding how they rank in their Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reuse (FAIR principles)

6 What issues agroforestry farmers face and what do they expect from digital tools to deal with these issues?

One of DigitAF project's aims is to understand the challenges faced by farmers, advisors, involved in agroforestry, and to find out if and how digital tools could help them. We first looked at research done by others in the past and we consulted various sources and experts in agriculture. Previous research showed that some challenges include increased labour, complex work, high costs, and administrative problems. However, these categories were broad, and we wanted to understand the specific issues better, so that we could develop better solutions and digital tools for everyone involved in agroforestry. To do this, we created a questionnaire that people could answer online using a tool called Google Forms to make it interactive. We tried to make it simple and not too long, focusing only on important questions, and we translated the survey in the native languages of our six Living Labs across Europe (Czech, Dutch, Finnish, German, and Italian). We shared our initial survey with a group of people working on the project and made improvements based on their feedback. We also looked at how to test our survey questions properly. Preliminary results show that implementing agroforestry faces common challenges across countries, including technical complexity and economic obstacles like large initial investments. Each country also has unique issues, such as data confidentiality in Germany, equipment and knowledge gaps in Italy, and administrative burdens in some regions. Collaboration, digital tools, and addressing these specific challenges are vital for successful agroforestry adoption. Follow us to get updates.

7 Biophysical models used in agroforestry studies: where to find and how to use them? What are their strengths and weaknesses?

We performed a literature search to find biophysical models (i.e. models that can predict the dynamics of a system based on biological and physical mechanisms) that can be used in agroforestry to predict tree and crop performances. We found 16 relevant models and analysed them in order to highlight the advantages and limits of each model in terms of reliability, ease of use and availability to farmers and researchers. Although some models can be found online freely or upon request, a majority of biophysical models used in agroforestry studies are either unavailable (i.e. the model has been described in the literature but cannot be found on the internet) or not working anymore (broken code due to lack of maintenance). For the models that are available, the main limit to their use is that they are often difficult to use (difficulty to install/run the model, parameterise it or interpret the results). Furthermore, the use of biophysical models often requires observed datasets to produce useful results. Nevertheless, biophysical models presents numerous advantages. Biophysical models provide a quantitative framework for understanding agroforestry systems, enabling precise predictions and assessments. They integrate data on soil, climate, and vegetation, facilitating data-driven decision-making for agroforestry practitioners. Models like APSIM Next Generation, Hi-sAFe, and DSSAT, identified in the study, demonstrated effectiveness, aiding in system optimization.

8 How to evaluate the biodiversity benefits of agroforestry? An overview of five example tools.

Agroforestry systems can enable continued food production whilst enhancing biodiversity. Within the DigitAF project, we are reviewing biodiversity tools by which farmers and others can predict and value biodiversity benefits of agricultural systems. From an initial evaluation, five example tools that could be of value to assess biodiversity levels on an agroforestry farm are: (1) The Biodiversity Integrated Assessment and Computation (B-INTACT) tool (<https://www.fao.org/documents/card/es/c/ca8762en>) from FAO comprises a quantitative (impact) and qualitative (biodiversity sensitivity and management practices) approach. (2) The Credit Point System (CPS) from Switzerland (<https://www.vogelwarte.ch/en/projects/habitats/scoring-with-biodiversity-farmers-enrich-nature>) assesses biodiversity using a points system based on the implementation of habitat management practices. (3) The Spatial Evidence for Natural Capital Evaluation (SENCE) tool (<https://envsys.co.uk/sence>) uses information on farm natural capital to provide a habitats status, indicating where to take action to deliver multiple benefits. (4) The Ecological Focus Area Calculator (EFA) tool (<http://sitem.herts.ac.uk/aeru/efa>) assesses impact of farm features on ecosystem services, biodiversity, and farm management. (5) The Cool Farm Tool (<https://coolfarm.org/the-tool>) helps to quantify baseline impacts on biodiversity using a scoring system, identify areas of improvement, and monitor progress. These and other tools to support agroforestry can be accessed through the DigitAF tool catalogue (<https://digitaf.eu/tools-database>).

9 When farmers, policymakers, value chain stakeholders and researchers meet

In the first year of DigitAF (2022-2023), six Living Labs (LL) were set up to better understand the needs of actor groups and to later test and evaluate digital tools. The LL, situated in the Czech Republic, Finland, Germany, Italy, The Netherlands and United Kingdom, were established in different European regions, with different pedoclimatic conditions, types of farming, and types of agroforestry systems. Although the composition of each LL differs, they all have a balanced composition in terms of the major actor groups that we targeted, e.g., policymakers (21 persons), practitioners (60 persons), those involved in the value chain (11 persons) and other actors such as NGOs, researchers and teachers (13 persons). All LL had an initial meeting in the period December 2022-March 2023 to introduce the Living Lab project, review the planning and the expectations. These meetings also included an initial exploration of the needs for digital tools for agroforestry. A second formal meeting of each LL took place in the period April-May of 2023. During these meetings, the results of the questionnaire of the LL in question were presented and certain themes that raised questions could be discussed in more depth. Thus far, a total of 14 formal meetings were organized for all living labs together. In addition, some LLs have taken the initiative to meet in a smaller, informal setting to explore sub-topics in more depth. The LL have so far proven themselves as a valuable instrument for identifying national and international needs. Now that the focus of the project is shifting more to developing specific tools, it is expected that the living labs will come together in subgroups.

10 What do you need to make the leap to agroforestry? Results of a survey in six countries about needs and expectations for agroforestry supporting tools.

In the first year of DigitAF project, we conducted a survey to understand how people involved in agroforestry use digital tools and what they need and want. We asked questions to learn about their opinions. The survey covered various topics related to agroforestry in Europe, like rules, nature, farming, money, and the use of digital tools.

We created an online survey using Google Forms that people could answer in English. Later, we translated it into other languages like Czech, Dutch, Finnish, German, and Italian so that more people could take part. Different regions had different numbers of people who answered, ranging from 3 in Finland to 20 in the Czech Republic. We heard from policymakers, farmers, and others involved in farming.

The results showed that many people want digital tools to help them plan and manage agroforestry. They also need tools to make financial decisions and track how well trees and crops are doing. People are interested in predicting and keeping an eye on things like carbon levels and biodiversity in their agroforestry systems. Everyone had suggestions to make these tools easier to use.

While there were some common themes, we also noticed that different regions had their unique needs. This means we can work together to come up with ideas and solutions that fit each area better. Our next steps include matching the needs we found with the tools and data available. We will work with the people who answered the survey to make sure the tools we choose are the right ones. Then, we will test and improve these tools based on their feedback. It's an ongoing process to make agroforestry better for everyone.

11 Farmer, policy-maker, stakeholder in the value chain of agroforestry products and services: DigitAF helps you find the right tool for your needs!

Do you want to design a new agroforestry system? To evaluate an existing system, or even to predict the impacts of agroforestry at the landscape scale? Do you want to find agroforestry products near you? Are you looking for subsidies to help sustain agroforestry or do you want to compare policies across countries? For all these tasks, and much more, there are digital tools that could help you. The only question is how to find them? In DigitAF, we have listed all these tools and we are currently testing and evaluating them for you. The catalogue will be available on the project website (<https://digitaf.eu/tools-database>) and will allow you to filter tools by task, system type and ease of use (cost, ease of installation, etc.).

12 How to tailor your communication to agroforestry stakeholders? The Buyer Persona methodology

A buyer persona is a fictional representation of someone who represents our target audience and notably the three group of stakeholders identified for DigitAF: policy actors, practitioners, beneficiary of agroforestry products and services. The Buyer Persona methodology keeps us focused on DigitAF's stakeholders priorities and not on what is important for each organization in the consortium. In order to actively involve our target audience in the project, we build a funnel consisting of four main stages: attract (the Buyer Persona visits DigitAF's website), capture (the Buyer Persona wants to know more), nurture (the Buyer Persona returns), close (the Buyer Persona is actively involved).

When we create a buyer persona for each stakeholder group, we think about a real person. We give the buyer persona a name, an age, details on his/her education, job, source of information and on what drives his/her decisions. Then, we answer some specific questions to know what this person is looking for in a project like DigitAF and notably related to:

- direct need (Why is he/she looking for agroforestry and related topics?)
- success factors (What does he/she expect from DigitAF?)
- possible barriers (Which negative expectations does he/she have regarding DigitAF?)
- decision criteria (What are the vital criteria for him/her to follow DigitAF?)
- motto and answer (What is his/her motto and what is our answer?).

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